

Table 1. Varietal reaction to leafhoppers and planthoppers, Varanasi, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a to			
	<i>N. lugens</i>	<i>S. furcifera</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>	<i>N. nigropictus</i>
OR34-16	S	MR	MR	MR
Jaya	MR	S	MR	S
CR202-2	S	MR	MR	MR
Culture 1	MR	MR	S	S
CR132-168-73	S	MR	S	MR
IR8	MR	S	MR	S
Saket 4	S	MR	MR	S
DR92	S	S	MR	S
RP79-24	S	S	MR	MR
Mtu 17	S	S	S	S
Nagina 22	S	S	MR	MR
RP79-27	S	S	S	S
CR142-2-10	S	S	S	S
RP79-5	S	S	S	S
Cauveri	S	MR	S	S
IR28	S	MR	S	MR
Pusa33	S	S	S	S
Jelhore	S	MR	S	MR
C7306	S	MR	S	S
FH109	S	S	S	S
IET5725	MR	MR	S	S
CR115-107	MR	S	S	S
TN1	S	S	S	S
Ptb 33	R	MR	MR	MR

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, and S = susceptible.

Table 2. Nymphal survival of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers on moderately resistant varieties at Varanasi, India.

Variety	Survival (%) of insect species ^a		
	<i>N. lugens</i>	<i>S. furcifera</i>	<i>Nephotettix</i> spp.
Jaya	63	—	73
IR28	—	67	87
RP79-24	—	—	70
Jelhore	83	77	73
IR8	70	—	77
OR34-16	—	67	73
CR202-2	—	80	73
Nagina 22	—	—	87
Saket 4	—	80	80
DR92	—	—	83
CR132-168-73	—	87	80
CR115-107	70	—	—
Culture	160	70	—
IET5725	67	77	—
Cauveri	—	57	—
C7306	—	73	—
TN1	97	100	100
Ptb33	43	47	53

^a— = not studied; a mixed population of *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* was used.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Performance of IR64 at Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRI)

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IR64 (IR18348-36-3-3) was evaluated at TNRRI in the 1983 International Rice Yield Nursery-Early trial and in 1984 yield trials. IR64 matured in 110-115 d

Performance of IR64 at TNRRI, Aduthurai, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Flowering duration (d)
	1983 kuruvai	1984 kuruvai		
		Trial 1	Trial 2	
IR64	3.4	5.6	5.3	65-70
TKM9	4.9	5.0	4.8	75-80
IR50	2.4	—	4.6	70-75
ADT36	—	—	4.7	80-85

and yielded 0.5 t/ha more than TKM9, IR50, and ADT36 (see table). It has short stature and long, slender grains, and is resistant to brown planthopper, gall midge, and yellowing syndrome, a serious disease in Tamil Nadu. ☞

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DEEP WATER

Elongation ability of deep water rice at two nitrogen levels

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Deep water Habiganj Aman II seeds

were sown in earthen pots with 8 kg soil and 0 or 8 g urea fertilizer per pot. The 5 replications had a pot each with 10 plants. Triple superphosphate and muriate of potash were applied at 5 g/pot. Five weeks after sowing, the pots were placed in concrete tanks,

flooded, and water was raised 10 cm/d for 9 d. A single seedling was taken from each pot every 2 d to record chlorophyll content and internode elongation.

Elongation rate of all plants increased for 4 d after flooding and then gradually